

Features Of Development Of Motivational-Value Orientation In Future Speech Therapists

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Abstract: *The article describes the development of motivational — value orientation in future speech therapists, the research and opinions of pedagogues and psychologists are described.*

Keywords — Defect, logopedic, feature, speech disorders, pedagogy, methodology, modern educational technologies.

INTRODUCTION.

Today, our honorable president pays great attention to youth and their education along with all other fields. "Every time I meet our young people, I get strength from your enthusiasm, my spirits rise like a mountain. I know very well that each of you is burning with the dream of serving our country and people. I appreciate you as the greatest wealth, priceless treasure of Uzbekistan," said Shavkat Mirziyoyev. No matter what reforms we try in our country, we will first of all rely on young people like you, your energy and determination. As you all know, today we have set great goals for ourselves.

We started to create the foundations of the Third Renaissance in our Motherland. We consider the family, pre-school education, school and higher education, as well as scientific and cultural centers to be the most important links of the future Renaissance. For this reason, we are implementing fundamental reforms in these areas. I believe that our selfless and patriotic young people, like you, will take an active part in creating a new foundation for the development of our country, and make a worthy contribution." The main goal of our country's policy is to educate today's advanced, mature and educated youth. And in practice, all plans and decisions are being implemented. All educational centers are equipped with modern innovative technologies. The goal is to raise the education system to a higher level, to form mature personnel who can compete with the world in every way. The correct and full development of speech is of great importance for every child who receives education in pre-school education institutions to become a fully formed person based on the needs of the times.

According to statistics, the number of speech defects is increasing worldwide, so prevention of speech defects in children and adolescents has become a growing problem. In our country, a lot of attention is paid to correctional-educational and pedagogical work with children with speech disabilities. A certain amount of progress has been achieved in early detection of speech deficiency, organization of correctional education, and solving the issue of methods of education.

A child's understanding of speech develops by making connections between the objects around him and the words spoken by adults. It is necessary to explain to parents who try to find out the child's desire through facial expressions or gestures that such behavior is wrong. Because in such a process, the child does not feel the need for voice reactions, sounds and pronunciation of words. Parents and pedagogues should always be aware of their own behavior and position in the process of raising speech-impaired children. Mutual encouragement, mutual respect, and interaction between family members play a significant role in the prevention of psychogenic reactive situations in children with speech impairment. It is important to develop a system of psychocorrective work with preschool children with speech development deficits.

The main condition for optimizing the process of training speech therapists at the faculty of special pedagogy is the design of a technological model of teaching, the use of an activity-based approach in teaching, which, in turn, emphasizes the importance of the student being able to apply theoretical knowledge in practice, meaning the proportionality of practical knowledge. The effectiveness of independent work within the study of speech therapy is high. The acquisition of activity-based (independent) educational technology by students is the most effective method in the conditions of close interaction between the teacher and the student, and this education, together with the acquisition of the content of speech therapy, is the personal qualities of the speech therapist's personality development. provides improvement. Studying information and communication technologies in the training of future speech therapists will be the basis for deep mastering of science. It is important to develop and effectively use the specific characteristics of the motivation given by the teacher for the effective use of modern educational technologies in science and practice. In special psychological-pedagogical literature, as well as in normative documents, the role of the use of development technologies in the professional activity of a speech therapist is incomparable.

The effectiveness of modern methods of training future speech therapists and educational technologies depends on their use of knowledge and skills in practical processes of the educational process, which ensures the professional skills of the student. The technological model of professional training for speech therapists makes it possible to change the quality

characteristics of the educational process in a positive direction. In training future speech therapists educational activities are carried out in special institutions in various facilities, organization of practice gives great results. Differentiation of speech defects allows to determine the level of competence in terms of types and forms of correctional approach, and also to prove the possibility of increasing this level and thereby create potential conditions for success in future professional activity.

Changes in higher pedagogical education require changes in the professional training of speech therapists. We need a modern professional who is knowledgeable and passionate about his profession. This concept is based on the fundamentally new social value and moral-psychological directions of society, the modern trends of the development of science, and the training of speech therapists, first of all, it is urgent to train a person who organically embodies high professionalism, intelligence, social maturity and creativity. Personal characteristics and shortcomings are eliminated by applying the technologies of development of motivational and valuable orientation of future speech therapists. An integral indicator of the maturity and development of the system of socially significant characteristics and professional and personal qualities of a modern speech therapist should be the readiness to create individual correction programs implemented in individual creative and professional pedagogical activities. The training of such a specialist is related to the creation of an effective educational environment, which is formed under the influence of such factors as the organization of special education, the continuity of speech therapy training, and the qualitative updating of technological conditions. It is important for speech therapists to develop personality traits based on the principles of humanitarianism, professional skills improvement and approach to activity, as well as to pass a higher pedagogical school. In connection with the professional training of modern speech therapists, it shows that personal-activity, multi-subjective and individual-creative approaches should be emphasized in the educational-pedagogical process. Its implementation is important for forecasting future professional activity, prioritizing personal and interpersonal relationships. The system of speech therapy education, which represents a holistic and at the same time continuous process of turning a student into a specialist, is recognized as one of the promising directions of training modeling at a modern pedagogical university. For this, it is important to ensure unity of theoretical and practical, general education and professional training. At the same time, it is important to humanize the students, develop the personality of the student, provide him with all-round speech therapy knowledge, form motivational — value orientations and ensure the intellectual and spiritual freedom of the future specialist. is one of the tasks. The technological model of the professional training of the future speech therapist includes clarifying the roles and tasks of the teacher and the student in the educational and pedagogical process. They are most effectively implemented in the structure of didactic management, which is a condition for the unique activity and creative self-awareness of a teacher of a higher pedagogical school.

The characteristic feature of the speech therapist's work is primarily the correction of speech disorders in children, but the modern speech therapist works with children of various categories, including children with various disorders, which requires the need to teach children. It can be considered as a practitioner who can move freely in related fields of science, is interested in research activities, is communicative, competent and can use innovative technologies in practical activities. A speech therapist requires a lot of knowledge and experience because they deal not only with deviations in speech development, but also with other psychophysical problems, that is, with children who have secondary disabilities. Thus, it is important that the speech therapist is ready to work in the correctional education system, and that he can successfully apply his theoretical knowledge in practice.

- It is necessary to have psychological training, i.e. the ability to set up pedagogical activities and work in an educational institution, to be able to act fairly in problematic situations;

- Scientific-theoretical training, i.e. availability of pedagogical, psychological and social knowledge necessary for qualified pedagogical activity;

- Practical training, i.e. availability of professional skills and qualifications formed at the level of demand;

- Pedagogical preparation, i.e. the presence of appropriate conditions for mastering teaching activities, the presence of personal qualities of developed professional importance;

- Physical fitness, i.e. health status, physical development must be in accordance with the requirements of pedagogical activity and professional activity.

Hello As a result, it is emphasized that through the above personal qualities, future speech therapists should be prepared for professional activities, skillful, lovers of their profession, and of course, continue to search. In the training of future speech therapists, it is an important process for them to be well-educated in all aspects and, of course, to have modern knowledge.

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